

Ligation of the Left Renal Vein in a Patient with Clear Cell Renal Carcinoma with Tumor Thrombosis of the Inferior Vena Cava and Right Renal Vein

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ABSTRACT

Left renal vein ligation is routinely performed to improve surgical exposure of the abdominal aorta, with documented short- and long-term safety. However, there is controversy in the literature regarding its impact on postoperative renal function. We will describe the diagnostic and surgical approach of a 54-year-old male patient with clear cell renal cell carcinoma and tumor thrombosis of the inferior vena cava and right renal vein. An inferior vena cava suprarenal filter was placed prior to right radical nephrectomy, partial inferior vena cava resection, appendectomy, and cholecystectomy with ligation of the left renal vein. This clinical case will help us understand the importance of using this procedure to achieve good surgical exposure and how to perform it safely in selected cases without significant deterioration of renal function, as demonstrated by the available literature.

KEYWORDS: Left renal vein, clear cell carcinoma, tumor thrombosis, inferior vena cava, radical nephrectomy.

ABBREVIATIONS: Left renal vein (LRV), right renal vein (RRV), inferior vena cava (IVC), glomerular filtration rate (GFR), computed tomography (CT).

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
04 July 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com/>

INTRODUCTION

The anatomy of the renal venous system has been less explored than the arterial system, despite its surgical relevance. The LRV is longer than the right, crossing anteriorly to the aorta in approximately 96–98% of cases, while its retroaortic arrangement is a variant present in approximately 2% of the population (1, 2, 3).

This vein receives tributaries such as the left gonadal vein, the suprarenal vein, and several lumbar veins, which constitute a rich collateral drainage network (1, 4).

Division or ligation of the LRV is frequently used to improve exposure of the abdominal aorta and its branches, especially during procedures such as aortic aneurysm repair or complex retroperitoneal surgeries (5, 6, 7, 8).

Although multiple studies have shown that this maneuver can be performed safely without significant repercussions on renal function, there is still controversy surrounding this maneuver (9, 10, 11).

Some publications have reported elevations in serum creatinine or decreased GFR following ligation, particularly in the absence of an adequately functioning collateral network (12, 13, 14, 15).

This case report aims to describe the diagnostic approach and surgical management of a patient with clear cell renal cell carcinoma and tumor thrombosis of the IVC and RRV. Treatment required ligation of the LRV without reconstruction, with favorable clinical and renal function outcomes.

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CASE DESCRIPTION

A 54-year-old male patient, originally from Tuxtla Gutiérrez, with a personal history unrelated to his current condition. He reported good hygiene habits, regular aerobic physical activity, and no history of smoking, alcohol use, or drug addiction. Surgical history included a pylorotomy in childhood and right inguinal mesh plasty. He also had a family history of a father who died of bladder cancer.

His condition began two months before admission with abdominal pain in the right flank and a progressive increase in abdominal girth. The pain suddenly increased to of 10/10 intensity, with no hematuria or other associated symptoms. Physical examination revealed a soft, depressible, and painful abdomen in the right flank, with a palpable mass measuring approximately 15 x 8 cm and of multinodular consistency. Initial laboratory studies showed leukocytes $5.9 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, hemoglobin 13.6 g/dL, hematocrit 40.8%, platelets $594 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, serum creatinine 1.1 mg/dL, and fibrinogen 594 mg/dL. The remaining parameters were normal.

A triphasic abdominal computed tomography scan revealed a right renal tumor measuring $17 \times 10 \times 11$ cm, with defined borders, heterogeneous enhancement, and extension into the IVC and RRV, with a filling defect and venous collateral network (Figure 1 and 2).

FIGURE 1. Axial (A) and sagittal (B) sections of contrast-enhanced abdominal CT, showing the dimensions of the right renal tumor, measuring 17x10x11 cm, the contours are defined, the contrast enhancement is heterogeneous, and tumor extension to the IVC and RRV is noted.

FIGURE 2. Coronal section of a CT scan of the abdomen with contrast in the venous phase, showing the IVC with a filling defect caused by a tumor thrombus, with associated collaterals (A); the abdominal aorta and ostium of the renal arteries are unchanged (B).

A Doppler ultrasound of the lower extremities ruled out deep vein thrombosis (Figure 3).

FIGURE 3. 3D reconstructions, showing the anatomical and vascular structure of the renal tumor and absence of opacification of the left renal vein.

Given the high thrombotic risk (CAPRINI >5), preoperative endovascular placement of a Greenfield adrenal filter at the T12 level was indicated as an alternative to anticoagulation, which was contraindicated due to the surgical risk of

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bleeding. The procedure was performed without complications, with simultaneous placement of a central venous catheter in the right internal jugular vein (Figure 4).

FIGURE 4. Fluoroscopy showing vena cava filter at the level of T12 in the suprarenal position.

During surgery, a tumor was found adherent to the IVC, with a tumor thrombus in the IVC and right renal vein. Right radical nephrectomy, 5 cm resection of the IVC, appendectomy, and cholecystectomy for adhesions were performed. To achieve adequate surgical exposure, the IVC was divided without reconstruction, in agreement with the vascular surgery team.

In the immediate postoperative period, the patient was admitted to the intermediate care unit, extubated, with adequate urine output (1 mL/kg/h) and without hemodynamic deterioration. Vasopressors were discontinued on the first day. Twenty-four hours later, the creatinine level rose to 1.6 mg/dL; fluid loading and diuretics were started. Left renal Doppler showed good perfusion and arteries with normal resistance indices (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5. Renal Doppler USG. When applying color Doppler, saturation is observed up to the periphery of the renal cortex.

Between postoperative days 2 and 4, creatinine peaked at 2.1 mg/dL, with a cystatin C GFR of 52 mL/min. Intensive hydration was maintained, with progressive improvement. On day 5, creatinine decreased to 1.8 mg/dL, and the patient

was discharged on day 7 with a creatinine of 1.6 mg/dL and stable renal function.

Histopathological examination revealed a clear cell carcinoma measuring 17 × 11 cm with invasion of the renal sinus, pyelocalyceal system, major vein, and perinephric lymph node (one-half positive). Renal capsule and ureteral margins were negative. Pathological stage: pT3a N1.

DISCUSSION

Division of the left renal vein (LRV) is a relatively frequently used maneuver during complex aortic or retroperitoneal surgery. Although some authors recommend routine reconstruction to prevent renal deterioration, multiple clinical studies have shown that ligation can be performed safely in patients with a functioning collateral network (1–4).

The LRV receives tributaries from the gonadal vein, adrenal vein, and lumbar veins, generating effective collateral circulation that allows drainage of the left kidney even after venous ligation (2, 3, 5).

This anatomy has been key to justifying the safety of the procedure in aortic surgery, retroperitoneal oncology, and kidney transplantation.

A retrospective study by Samson et al. (4), which included 56 patients undergoing LRV division without reconstruction, did not show significant deterioration in serum creatinine or glomerular filtration rate (GFR) in the short or long term. Similar results were observed by Elsharawy et al. (7) and Komori et al. (8), who also reported adequate hemodynamic tolerance after venous transection.

In a recent 2021 meta-analysis, Huang et al (9), evaluated 240 patients who underwent LRV ligation during extensive retroperitoneal resections. The study confirmed that while transient creatinine elevation may occur in the immediate postoperative period, there is no clinically significant impact on renal function at 1-year follow-up (6).

In this case, the patient presented a transient elevation of creatinine levels to 2.1 mg/dL, with progressive recovery under conservative management. Preservation of renal perfusion was demonstrated with Doppler ultrasound and recovery of GFR by cystatin C, consistent with what has been described in the literature.

Regarding the oncological approach, tumor extension to the inferior vena cava (IVC) is characteristic of clear cell renal cell carcinoma. The Neves-Zincke classification categorizes tumor invasion into four levels according to its extension: from the renal vein (level I) to the right atrium (level IV) (9, 10).

This case was classified as level II (infrahepatic), which allowed for segmental tumor resection without extracorporeal circulation or atriotomy.

The pathological stage pT3aN1 correlates with locally advanced disease, requiring radical nephrectomy and close follow-up. The use of an adrenal IVC filter is supported in

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patients with a contraindication to anticoagulation, as a prophylactic measure against pulmonary embolism (11). Overall, current evidence supports that IVC ligation can be performed safely in selected settings, with adequate preoperative evaluation and postoperative monitoring, especially in cancer patients with vascular compromise (12-15).

CONCLUSION

Left renal vein ligation, in the context of complex tumor resection with vascular compromise, can be performed safely in selected patients. In this case, favorable renal functional recovery was demonstrated, without major complications, validating the literature supporting its use as an adjunct technique to achieve adequate surgical exposure. Clinical and hemodynamic follow-up confirms that there was no significant deterioration in renal function in the short term.

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